

MARKETING COMMUNICATION AND CONSUMER BEHAVIOR IN MEDIATING ROLE ON SOCIAL MEDIA TO MOVIES BUSINESS PERFORMANCE

Dr. PONGSAWEE SUPANONTH

Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Thailand. Email: Pongsawee.su@ssru.ac.th

Abstract

The objective of the present study is to investigate the role of marketing communication (MC), consumer behavior and social media in business performance (BP) of movies in Thailand. This study achieved this objective with the help of quantitative research approach. The quantitative research approach is followed by using a questionnaire. The survey questionnaire was developed with the help of previous studies. Literature was used to design a survey questionnaire. Data Collection of this study is made from various companies related to the filmmaking in Thailand. The employees of these organizations are considered to get the response with the help of questionnaire. The respondents of the study include producers, directors, artists and various employees of companies related to the movie making. 384 questionnaires were distributed among the respondents and data analyses were carried out with the help of statistical tool. The results of the study highlighted that MC and consumer behavior has important role to promote movie BP. Furthermore, social media playing an intervening role between MC, consumer behavior and BP. The relationship between MC, consumer behavior and social media has significant importance to promote movies BP in Thailand.

Keywords: Marketing communication, consumer behavior, social media, BP, Thailand film industry.

1. INTRODUCTION

Along with the other industries film industry is one of the important industries (Baranov & Butymova, 2021; Hu, Xu, Tong, & Razi, 2022). It has significant importance for several nations because it has significant contribution to the nation's economy. This industry is growing rapidly with the increase in technology. The most famous industry worldwide is Indian film industry which is called Bollywood. It is one of the oldest Industries globally. This industry has contribution to the economy of the India at higher level. Along with the Indian film Industry the Hollywood industry is also one of the major film industries.

In addition to various other countries the film industry of Thailand is also on the growing stage. This industry is competing with the other nations; however, it requires significant improvements to compete with the top film industries worldwide. This industry is also having significant importance for Thailand due to several reasons; however, it is important to promote this industry to get benefits on wider scope. Although this industry already contributing to the nation's economic development along with other benefits, however it is needed to promote through movies business performance (BP). However, the film industry of Thailand is facing several issues related to the BP. As BP is one of the most important elements to survive in a competitive business market (Chi, Kilduff, & Gargeya, 2009; Prajogo & Oke, 2016). In the current competition of film industry, the competition is increasing gradually which has adverse effect on various film industries. The film industries which are on the growing stage are facing

several issues due to the other stable competitors, therefore, Thailand film industry is one of the industries which is on the growing stage and requires significant level of strategies to promote movies BP. This industry is lacking with BP as compared to the other industries such as Hollywood and Bollywood. The low performers of this industry have negative effect on overall performance of this industry globally. Therefore, it is important to promote BP of movies. As higher performance is required for the survival in the competitive business market (Rosenzweig, Roth, & Dean Jr, 2003). The film industry is having low performance which cannot enhance the long-term benefits in the competitive market. The movies developed by the Thailand film industry need to promote performance which should have significant contribution to the overall BP of this industry with the help of different strategies. The BP of movies should be promoted to enhance the overall BP of film industry.

Therefore, the current study is one of the attempts to promote movies BP in Thailand. According to the current studies the movies BP can be promoted with the help of social media. Social media platform can be used to enhance the BP of movies as social media is in the excess of each individual or general public. The marketing of movies can be promoted with the help of social media which has the ability to enhance BP. Hence this study commended marketing communication (MC) (Falahat, Ramayah, Soto-Acosta, & Lee, 2020) as an important tool to promote BP with the help of social media. The current study also recommended consumer behavior as an important element to promote BP in relation to the social media. According to the current study, MC and consumer behavior in relation to the social media has the ability to enhance BP.

Therefore, the objective of this study is to observe the role of MC, consumer behavior and social media to promote movies BP in Thailand. This study considers the relationship between MC, consumer behavior, social media and BP in Thailand. This relationship has major importance for the literature as this relationship in film industry is not considered by the previous studies. Although there are a number of studies available on film industry (Gilardi et al., 2020; Solidoro & Viscusi, 2020), however the effect of MC and consumer behavior is not examined on movies BP in Thailand along with the mediating role of social media. Therefore, the current study is contributing to the body of knowledge in the field of film industry.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Framework Development

The framework of the current study included various variables. The independent variables include MC and consumer behavior. The mediating variable in the study is social media and dependent variable is BP. The BP of movies is considered in this study as major research area. The relationship between these variables is considered by considering the gaps in the literature. Although several studies are available on BP (Wang et al., 2020; Yingfei et al., 2022), however the BP of movies is not considered in previous studies. Several studies mentioned the BP of film industry or the BP of movies, however the role of social media along with MC and consumer behavior is not considered. In this study the mediating role of social media is considered in MC and BP of film industry. The mediating role of social media is also

considered between consumer behavior and BP of movies. These mediating effects are really examined in previous studies. Therefore, most of the relationship considered in the current study is not tested by the previous studies. In this way this study addressed the relationship between MC, consumer behavior social media and BP in relation to the movies in Thailand. This relationship is highlighted in Figure 1 as theoretical framework of the study.

Figure 1: Framework of the Study

2.2 Hypotheses Development

Marketing has the important role to promote business services as well as products. All the businesses need marketing activities to get success in services and products. That is the reason, several preceding studies have highlighted that marketing has positive effect on BP. Therefore, marketing is key to the BP (Al-Dmour et al., 2020; Khan, Royhan, Rahman, Rahman, & Mostafa, 2020). Similarly marketing also has vital importance in film industry. To promote newly developed movies, it is important to help these movies with the help of marketing activities. That is the reason the current study considered MC (Shankar et al., 2021) to enhance movies BP. MC involves advertisement, personal selling, direct marketing events experiences and other marketing along with the sales promotion. All these elements of MC have the potential to improve BP by creating the level of awareness among the general public related to the movies. This is recommended and proposed that MC has positive role to influence movies BP. Moreover, currently social media marketing is more active (Chen & Lin, 2019) among the business setting. Most of the business organizations are trying to help BP with the help of social media marketing. Social media is one of the most important roles to promote and to enhance the responsiveness among the people linked to the definite product. To introduce new movies, it is needed to promote movie performance in which the role of social media is most important in relation to the MC. Marketing efforts can be enhanced with the help of social media. Therefore, the involvement of social media between MC and BP has the potential to strengthen the BP in film industry. Social media is based on various media's such as TV, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, YouTube and various other channels. All these channels can promote

various products of different companies which has the potential to improve BP. According to the present study, MC has relationship with social media which causes to promote business activities in film industries. Therefore, this study proposes that MC has effect on social media which lead to the BP. Therefore, it can be hypothesized that;

Hypothesis 1: MC has relationship with BP.

Hypothesis 2: MC has relationship with social media.

Moreover, consumer behavior is another important element of BP(Hermina, Siboro, & Halimah, 2020; Kim, Lee, & Han, 2020).BP of movie is also depended on the consumer behavior. Consumer behavior is the investigation about individuals' different organizations along with all different activities in relation to the purchase or use of products and services. The consumer behavior is based on the emotions of consumers and attitude of the consumer. All these elements such as emotions, attitude and preference of the consumer have major effect on the BP. It is highlighted by the earlier studies that consumer behavior has significant effect on BP (Agustin et al., 2021; Ong et al., 2021). The numerous preceding studies have scrutinized the association between consumer behavior and BP among several Industries; however, it is really considered in relation to the movies BP. Therefore, film industry is ignored by the previous studies in relation to the consumer behavior along with the social media. There is a key connection between social media and consumer behavior which has influence on BP. Consumer behavior generally effect on the adoption of social media channels. The consumer behavior towards the acceptance of social media channels leads towards the increase in awareness of various products and services which causes to enhance the BP. A positive consumer behavior to adopt social media channels can increase the BP because it has the ability to enhance the interest of the people to purchase any product or services. Similarly in the film industry the movie's BP is depends on the consumer behavior that how consumer perceives the newly introduced movie. The relationship between social media and consumer behavior has significant effect on movies business. In this direction the current study proposed that consumer behavior has effect on social media which causes to increase or decrease the movie business. Therefore, it is proposed that;

Hypothesis 3: Consumer behavior has relationship with BP.

Hypothesis 4: Consumer behavior has relationship with social media.

Hypothesis 5: Social media has relationship with BP.

Hypothesis 6: Social media mediates the relationship between MC and BP.

Hypothesis 7: Social media mediates the relationship between consumer behavior and BP.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this study the objective is achieved by adopting quantitative research approach to inspect the relationship between variables. In addition to the quantitative research method, the present study used cross sectional research design. Although longitudinal research design is also available to examine the relationship between variable, however, the cross-sectional research design is most suitable in the current study. Several other studies in relation to the BP, MC, consumer behavior and social media are also considered cross-sectional research design. Therefore, the nature of this study is similar with the quantitative research method by using cross sectional research design.

Moreover, it is observed that different studies in the field of BP, MC, consumer behavior and social media are considered questionnaire survey. Questionnaire survey was preferred by the previous studies to investigate about BP among several fields, there for; this study also preferred questionnaire survey. The questionnaire survey is carried out in this study for data collection. This study adopted several measures from literature and design a complete questionnaire survey in which scale items related to the BP was addressed in relation to the sales, return on equity, return on assets and profit in relation to competitors. Furthermore, social media scale items are also considered in relation to the role of social media in several marketing activities. MC factors are considered to measure the variable MC. Furthermore, this study also uses various scale items related to the consumer behavior from previous studies.

To collect the data, the current study distributed survey questionnaires in Thailand among various filmmaking company, clubs and several other organizations related to the film industry. Data collection is made from film industry in Thailand and the respondents of the study was the directors in relation to the film industry, artists, producers and various other employees in film industry. The questionnaire was distributed with the help of these organizations in Thailand. During data collection, it is observed that the respondent is actually involved in movie making activities; therefore these respondents can fill the questionnaire in right direction. And before data collection, the objective of this study was well clarified to the respondents and it is guided to the respondents that this response is important to get the results of the study in relation to the BP of movies. Finally, this study distributed 384 questionnaires among the respondents in Thailand. From this distributed questionnaire, 50% response was observed and this study received 192 questionnaires for data analysis.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis of the study carried out after data cleaning. It is used to examine the errors in the data. In this process, the current study addressed data screening to fix the errors related to the data such as missing value in the data and outlier in the data along with the normality of the data. All these errors are important to identify before to check the relationship between variables. Therefore, after ascertaining the cleaned data, it is presented in Table 1 and shows that there is no error.

Table 1: Data Statistics

	No.	Missing	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness
MC1	1	0	2.042	2	1	5	0.976	1.845	1.39
MC2	2	0	2.065	2	1	5	0.954	2.014	1.333
MC3	3	0	1.947	2	1	5	1.104	1.403	1.393
MC4	4	0	2.094	2	1	5	1.276	0.475	1.237
MC5	5	0	2.012	2	1	5	1.15	0.575	1.142
CB1	6	0	1.936	2	1	5	1.055	0.824	1.155
CB2	7	0	2.006	2	1	5	1.046	1.183	1.257
CB3	8	0	2.012	2	1	5	0.984	1.364	0.991
CB4	9	0	2.053	2	1	5	1.067	0.741	1.12
CB5	10	0	1.895	2	1	5	0.943	0.779	1.211
SM1	11	0	1.971	2	1	5	0.947	1.124	1.325
SM2	12	0	1.778	2	1	5	0.954	2.392	1.52
SM3	13	0	1.889	2	1	5	0.988	1.244	1.254
SM4	14	0	2.152	2	1	5	1.071	0.221	0.932
BP1	15	0	1.754	2	1	5	0.857	3.591	1.621
BP2	16	0	2	2	1	5	1.119	1.184	1.315
BP3	17	0	2.058	2	1	5	1.122	1.119	1.286
BP4	18	0	2.023	2	1	5	1.043	0.908	1.108
BP5	19	0	2.193	2	1	5	1.171	0.188	0.984

After data cleaning this study investigated the most suitable data analysis software to observe the relationship between variables. Previous studies recommended several statistical tools to observe the relationship between different variables, however, all the data analysis tools cannot apply on a study. Therefore, it is really important to identify most suitable data analysis tool. In this way the current study considered the most relevant and recommended data analysis tool. This study used Smart PLS 3 for data examination which is most popular software to examine the relationship between variables with the help of questionnaire survey (Chairatana, 2021; Hair et al., 2017; Khan et al., 2019). Figure 2 displays the measurement model of PLS. The measurement model is used to inspect the reliability of the scale items. Therefore, factor loadings were examined in this part of data analysis. The factor loading is emphasized in Figure 2 and Table 2. It displays that MC is measured by using five items, consumer behavior is measured by using five items, social media is measured by using four items and finally BP is evaluated through using five scale items. Table 2 demonstrates that all the items have factor loading above 0.5 a minimum level to achieve all the scale items in this study. The items with factor loading below 0.5 were deleted from the current study.

Figure 2: Measurement Model

Table 2: Factor Loadings

Variables	Items	Loadings	Alpha	CR	AVE
BP	BP1	0.72	0.764	0.841	0.517
	BP2	0.572			
	BP3	0.757			
	BP4	0.783			
	BP5	0.745			
Consumer Behavior	CB1	0.804	0.842	0.888	0.613
	CB2	0.785			
	CB3	0.803			
	CB4	0.775			
	CB5	0.745			
Marketing Communication	MC1	0.739	0.817	0.873	0.579
	MC2	0.749			
	MC3	0.797			
	MC4	0.722			
	MC5	0.796			
Social Media	SM1	0.792	0.771	0.853	0.592
	SM2	0.749			
	SM3	0.74			
	SM4	0.794			

Composite reliability is the important to measure of reliability of scale developed in the current study, therefore, this study considered composite liability for all the scale items including. Although the reliability is also examined with the help of Cronbach Alpha, however composite liability is latest and more preferable in PLS. Table 2 shows that MC, consumer behavior, social media and BP has composite liability above 0.7 which is the minimum criteria to achieve in the present study. This study examined convergent validity according to previous studies which is important to achieve before to inspect the connection between variables. In this study, convergent validity is examined by using recommended criteria by previous studies. Convergent validity can be measured through composite liability and average variance extracted. According to the literature composite liability must not be less than 0.7 and AVE must not be less than 0.5 to attain convergent validity. All these criteria are fulfilled by the results of the current study as shown in Table 2. Nonetheless this study also addressed discriminant validity which is also one of the important measures of scale validity which must be achieved before to inspect the relationship among variables. In this study discriminant validity is considered by using HTMT_{0.9} ratio as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: HTMT

	BP	Consumer Behavior	MC	Social Media
BP				
Consumer Behavior	0.714			
MC	0.651	0.621		
Social Media	0.728	0.751	0.77	

Structural model of PLS shows the relationship results (Ali et al., 2018; Hair et al., 2019; Mohammed et al., 2022; Yin, Wang, Xu, Wan, & Wang, 2022). Structural model is used to test the effect of MC, consumer behavior and social media on BP of movies. Outcomes of structural model are given in Table 4. In Table 4; it is shown that the effect of MC on BP is significant. The effect of MC on social media is also significant. The effect of consumer behavior on BP is significant. Furthermore, the effect of consumer behavior is significant on social media; finally, it is proved that the direct effect of social media on BP is also significant. Hence, all the direct hypothesis is supported as all the relationships have a value above 1.96.

Table 4: Direct Effect Results

	Beta	M	SD	T Statistics	P Values
Consumer Behavior ->BP	0.131	0.129	0.032	3.921	0
Consumer Behavior ->social media	0.738	0.742	0.099	7.416	0
MC->BP	0.439	0.45	0.058	7.599	0
MC->social media	0.056	0.05	0.028	1.991	0.046
Social Media ->BP	0.352	0.345	0.088	4.02	0

Along with the direct effect of social media on BP, the indirect effect of social media on BP is also tested in the current study. First, the mediation effect of social media is inspected between

MC and BP. Second, the mediation effect of social media is considered between consumer behavior and BP. Both the mediation effect is given in Table 5. Results given in Table 5 shows that both the mediation effects are significant and positive. It indicated that social media facilitates BP of movies with the help of transferring the positive effect of MC on consumer behavior and BP.

Table 5: Indirect Effect Results

	Beta	M	SD	T Statistics	P Values
Consumer Behavior ->social media ->BP	0.259	0.259	0.083	3.122	0.002
MC->social media ->BP	0.02	0.014	0.01	1.999	0.045

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

To address the role of MC, consumer behavior and social media in BP of film industry, the present study proposed various hypotheses with the help of literature. In this way, this study develops seven hypotheses to examine the relationship between MC, consumer behavior; social media and BP. Hypothesis are based on the direct hypotheses by examining the effect of independent variable on dependent variable and mediating variable on dependent variable. Two hypotheses were developed to examine the mediating role of social media. The hypothesis 1 in the current study depicts the relationship between MC and BP. The results of this hypothesis are in line with the previous studies as this study proves that MC has pivotal role in BP. It is proved that the BP of film industry can be promoted with the help of MC. The increase in MC among the companies related to the film industry can enhance newly developed movies BP. This relationship is consistent among various other fields and among various other industries which was considered by the previous studies. As previous studies highlighted that MC has positive relationship with BP (Falihat et al., 2020; Martin, Javalgi, & Ciravegna, 2020; Picichio & Toaldo, 2021) and several business organizations. Furthermore, hypothesis 2 of this study is developed to examine the relationship between consumer behavior and BP. Along with the hypothesis 1 and this hypothesis is also significant and denotes the positive effect of consumer behavior on BP. The results of this hypothesis shows that the positive consumer behavior always lead towards the BP of newly developed movies. This hypothesis is also considered with the previous studies as it is highlighted by other studies that consumer behavior is important to enhance BP. And both the independent variables namely MC and consumer behavior has positive role to promote BP of movies in Thailand.

Hypothesis 3 and hypothesis 4 are grounded on the relationship between MC, consumer behavior and social media. The hypothesis 3 shows that MC has positive effect on social media. It indicates that MC has the ability to influence social media. MC with the help of social media can generate positive effects for BP. Similarly, consumer behavior and social media also has relationship with each other which has effect on BP of movies. Strong the connection between consumer behavior and social media strong will be the BP. Therefore, hypothesis 3 and hypothesis 4 highlighted that MC and consumer behavior has the ability to influence BP positively with help of social media. This study also examines the effect of social media on BP

directly with the help of hypothesis 5 which indicated that BP of movies can be promoted through social media. More the involvement of social media in MC activities along with the consumer behavior can enhance BP; therefore, the connection between MC and consumer behavior and social media is most important to enhance movies BP in Thailand.

Additionally, this study examines the indirect relationship of social media which has influence on BP. In this way the current study examines the mediating role of social media between MC and BP. This mediation effect is considered in hypothesis 6 which is significant. It indicated that social media has positive role to transfer the positive effect of MC on BP. Social media is one of the facilitators to promote BP with the help of MC. Nevertheless, consumer behavior also influences BP with the help of social media. Social media can promote business communication by intervening the relationship of consumer behavior and BP, therefore, social media playing an important role to transfer the positive effect of MC and consumer behavior on BP.

6. IMPLICATIONS

The current study tested a unique model in film industry of Thailand. Literature has considered film industry previously, however BP of film industry is in relation to the BP of newly developed movies is really considered in literature. In this direction by considering BP of newly developed movies is one of the major contributions in literature. By considering this relationship, this study started a new debate in relation to the BP of movies. Previous studies considered BP of overall film industry; however, this study considered the BP of newly developed movies in Thailand which is a unique contribution and one of the important areas of study in the field of film industry. In addition to this, the current study used as social media as one of the major facilitator of movies BP. This is very first study which is examine the role of social media in movie BP in Thailand. Furthermore, this study used MC along with the consumer behavior to promote social media and BP of movies which is unique and ignored by the previous studies in the literature. Moreover, this study is more beneficial for practitioners as this study provided important points for the practitioners to promote film industry performance. This study proved that social media has given role to promote BP of movies. The increase in BP; a movie can increase the overall BP of film industry. Therefore, this study has vital insights and this study recommended the practitioners to promote social media in relation to the MC which has the ability to enhance BP of movies. Additionally, this study is also recommended the movie making companies, various producer and artists to focus on MC factors and consumer behavior to promote newly developed movies BP along with the consideration of important role of social media.

References

- Agustin, K. I., & Handayani br Tarigan, N. H. (2021). The Influence of Consumer Behavior and Environmental Factors Through Business Strategies on Marketing Performance of MSMEs in West Java During the Pandemic Covid-19. *Psychology and Education Journal*, 58(3), 655-663.
- Al-Dmour, H., Asfour, F., Al-Dmour, R., & Al-Dmour, A. (2020). Validation of the impact of marketing knowledge management on BP via digital financial innovation as a mediating factor. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*.

- Ali, F., Rasoolimanesh, S. M., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., & Ryu, K. (2018). An assessment of the use of partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) in hospitality research. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*.
- Baranov, V., & Butymova, D. (2021). COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGES OF STREAMING PLATFORMS BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE FILM INDUSTRY (ON THE EXAMPLE OF COMPANY "NETFLIX"). *Международный научно-исследовательский журнал*(8 (110) Часть 4), 104-109.
- Chairatana, P. (2021). The image of historical tourism in the area of the Ayutthaya Historical Park affecting the decision to visit of Thai tourists in Phra Nakhon Si Ayutthaya. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(8), 2414-2419.
- Chen, S.-C., & Lin, C.-P. (2019). Understanding the effect of social media marketing activities: The mediation of social identification, perceived value, and satisfaction. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 140, 22-32.
- Chi, T., Kilduff, P. P., & Gargeya, V. B. (2009). Alignment between business environment characteristics, competitive priorities, supply chain structures, and firm BP. *International Journal of productivity and performance management*.
- Falahat, M., Ramayah, T., Soto-Acosta, P., & Lee, Y.-Y. (2020). SMEs internationalization: The role of product innovation, market intelligence, pricing and marketing communication capabilities as drivers of SMEs' international performance. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 152, 119908.
- Gilardi, F., White, A., Cheng, S., Sheng, J., Song, W., & Zhao, Y. (2020). How online video platforms could support China's independent microfilm (short film) makers and enhance the Chinese film industry. *Cultural Trends*, 29(1), 35-49.
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., & Thiele, K. O. (2017). Mirror, mirror on the wall: a comparative evaluation of composite-based structural equation modeling methods. *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, 45(5), 616-632.
- Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., Gudergan, S. P., Fischer, A., Nitzl, C., & Menictas, C. (2019). Partial least squares structural equation modeling-based discrete choice modeling: an illustration in modeling retailer choice. *Business Research*, 12(1), 115-142.
- Herminalina, N., Siboro, E., & Halimah, Y. (2020). Total Market Demand Expansion Strategy Based on Personal Consumer Behavior and Value Proposition to Achieve Marketing Performance in SME Business Players in Bandung City During the Pandemic Covid-19. *Solid State Technology*, 63(3), 5084-5095.
- Hu, J., Xu, J., Tong, L., & Razi, U. (2022). The dynamic role of film and drama industry, green innovation towards the sustainable environment in China: fresh insight from NARDL approach. *Economic Research-Ekonomiska Istraživanja*, 1-18.
- Khan, E. A., Royhan, P., Rahman, M. A., Rahman, M. M., & Mostafa, A. (2020). The impact of enviropreneurial orientation on small firms' BP: The mediation of green marketing mix and eco-labeling strategies. *Sustainability*, 12(1), 221.
- Khan, G. F., Sarstedt, M., Shiao, W.-L., Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., & Fritze, M. P. (2019). Methodological research on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM): an analysis based on social network approaches. *Internet Research*.
- Kim, J. J., Lee, M. J., & Han, H. (2020). Smart hotels and sustainable consumer behavior: Testing the effect of perceived performance, attitude, and technology readiness on word-of-mouth. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(20), 7455.

- Martin, S. L., Javalgi, R. R. G., & Ciravegna, L. (2020). Marketing capabilities and international new venture performance: The mediation role of marketing communication and the moderation effect of technological turbulence. *Journal of Business Research*, 107, 25-37.
- Mohammed, M., Shafiq, N., Al-Mekhlafi, A.-B. A., Rashed, E. F., Khalil, M. H., Zawawi, N. A., . . . Sadis, A. M. (2022). The Mediating Role of Policy-Related Factors in the Relationship between Practice of Waste Generation and Sustainable Construction Waste Minimisation: PLS-SEM. *Sustainability*, 14(2), 656.
- Ong, A. K. S., Cleofas, M. A., Prasetyo, Y. T., Chuenyindee, T., Young, M. N., Diaz, J. F. T., . . . Redi, A. A. N. P. (2021). Consumer behavior in clothing industry and its relationship with open innovation dynamics during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 7(4), 211.
- Pisicchio, A. C., & Toaldo, A. M. M. (2021). Integrated marketing communication in hospitality SMEs: analyzing the antecedent role of innovation orientation and the effect on market performance. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 27(7), 742-761.
- Prajogo, D. I., & Oke, A. (2016). Human capital, service innovation advantage, and BP: The moderating roles of dynamic and competitive environments. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*.
- Rosenzweig, E. D., Roth, A. V., & Dean Jr, J. W. (2003). The influence of an integration strategy on competitive capabilities and BP: an exploratory study of consumer products manufacturers. *Journal of operations management*, 21(4), 437-456.
- Shankar, V., Grewal, D., Sunder, S., Fossen, B., Peters, K., & Agarwal, A. (2021). Digital marketing communication in global marketplaces: A review of extant research, future directions, and potential approaches. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*.
- Solidoro, A., & Viscusi, G. (2020). Digital transformation and business model innovation in the film industry: The case of movieday. *it Technology and Creativity* (pp. 239-265): Springer.
- Wang, Z., Zhang, J., Ji, S., Meng, C., Li, T., & Zheng, Y. (2020). Predicting and ranking box office revenue of movies based on big data. *Information Fusion*, 60, 25-40.
- Yin, Q., Wang, Y., Xu, Z., Wan, K., & Wang, D. (2022). Factors influencing green transformation efficiency in China's mineral resource-based cities: Method analysis based on IPAT-E and PLS-SEM. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 330, 129783.
- Yingfei, Y., Mengze, Z., Zeyu, L., Ki-Hyung, B., Avotra, A. A. R. N., & Nawaz, A. (2022). Green logistics performance and infrastructure on service trade and environment-measuring firm's performance and service quality. *Journal of King Saud University-Science*, 34(1), 101683.